

Developing a risk assessment approach for forest fire at the rural-urban interface: potential of the Wildfire Threat Analysis framework for the UK

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Summary:

Wildfires in the rural-urban interface harm forest assets and related ecosystem services, damage adjacent housing, social infrastructure and transport links, and pose health risks. We developed a framework for systematically assessing the threat of wildfire in a UK context based on New Zealand's Wildfire Threat Analysis (WTA). WTA was evaluated for a pilot area in Southern England where urban assets are close to fire-prone forest and heath environments.

WTA comprises three modules: Risk of Ignition, Hazard (fire spread and intensity) and Values at Risk (assets). Fire occurrence data were analysed with Geographical Information System map layers and evidence from an

informed stakeholder panel. A set of maps was produced for two of the three modules; Risk of Ignition and Values at Risk, which highlight target areas for improved wildfire prevention and response. Empirical evidence on wildfire risk differed from stakeholder views, and priorities varied between stakeholder sectors. WTA is therefore not an objective decision support tool, but instead a valuable 'discussion support' tool for forest managers to help reconcile different stakeholder needs, develop emergency planning and encourage land management solutions that reduce wildfire threat. The consultative process is best suited to local or landscape scales, with empirically-based methods at a national scale.

Introduction

Wildfires are surprisingly common in the British countryside – in financial years 2009/10 to 2016/17, almost 260,000 wildfires burned an estimated 37,000ha across all vegetation types in England (Forestry Commission England, 2019). Wildfire poses particular threats at the rural-urban interface where open countryside is adjacent to suburban housing, busy transport corridors and public infrastructure such as hospitals and schools, often built with little regard for local fire risk (Gazzard et al., 2016).

In the UK forestry sector wildfire risk has long been recognised (Rouse, 1959) but climate change is likely to make the wildfire problem worse (Wentworth and Shoter, 2019). Increased risk is acknowledged in the UK Forestry Standard, which identifies wildfire as a threat to be included in contingency planning (Forestry Commission, 2017). The Forestry Commission's (2014) Practice Guide to building wildfire resilience is a first attempt to provide modern guidance in the UK, using toolkits based on Forest Management Plan principles, including a wildfire risk assessment process. Yet, the guide does not measure wildfire risk. Assessment tools are therefore needed to

reflect the wide variety of land cover within UK forests. Further, an integrated land-use-risk-management approach is essential because most fires start in open habitats before spreading into woodland.

Wildfire Threat Analysis (WTA) represents a possible risk management approach to wildfire in the UK. The WTA approach was first developed in Canada and successfully implemented on a regional scale in New Zealand (Gibson and Pearce, 2007). WTA is a systematic method of identifying wildfire threat using Geographical Information Systems (GIS), and analysed as a combination of three modules:

- **Risk of Ignition** – ignition potential; how likely is a fire to start at a point, based on land cover, density of ignition sources from public access, power lines, transport, etc.
- **Hazard** – potential fire behaviour, or fire intensity and rate of spread.
- **Values at Risk** – assets exposed to the fire, including life, property and ecosystem services.

WTA generates a set of maps for each of the modules, which are combined into an overall threat map; the level of threat is a linear combination of ignition potential, likely fire behaviour and the assets at risk. A key ingredient of WTA is the incorporation of stakeholder knowledge elicited from cross-sector stakeholder panels, which are consulted at each stage of the WTA process.

In this paper we describe a project to evaluate and adapt the New Zealand WTA framework as a method for systematically assessing wildfire threat in a UK context, particularly in the rural-urban interface where urban assets are close to fire-prone forests and heaths. We outline the development of map layers for 'Risk of Ignition' and 'Values at Risk' modules. Unfortunately, a 'Hazard' layer could not be developed because fire climate information was not available. We have evaluated WTA for use in strategic decision-making by UK forest managers and planners, emergency officers and fire services. A more detailed account of the study is given by Kazmierczak et al. (2014).

The WTA procedure

WTA was tested in an 11 by 12km study area centred on Crowthorne Wood and Swinley Forest, on the borders of Berkshire, Surrey and Hampshire. This rural-urban interface

area has a complex mixture of landownership and land use: urban housing and infrastructure lie adjacent to a mosaic of forest and heath habitats. A serious wildfire incident, the 'Swinley Forest Fire', occurred in May 2011 (Oxborough and Gazzard, 2011), allowing us to draw on the experience and expertise of land and civil contingency managers involved in the incident. This fire threatened national infrastructure including a high-security hospital, the Transport Research Laboratory and a trunk fuel pipeline. Houses were evacuated, schools were closed and local businesses incurred significant losses.

Where possible, we used open sources of spatial data or those owned and shared by Government agencies alongside Ordnance Survey information, and location-specific data from Bracknell Forest Council and the Forestry Commission. Land use was based on the Land Cover Map 2007 (Morton et al., 2011) combined with the National Forest Inventory map (Forest Research, 2020). Fire point data from April 2009 were available in a national Fire Service dataset – the Incident Recording System (IRS) (Forestry Commission England, 2019).

The datasets allowed spatial analysis of fire point distribution relative to mapped features such as land cover type. Results could then be compared to stakeholders' own

Table 1. Comparison of relative Risk of Ignition scores for final land cover classes using empirical method based on Incident Recording System (IRS) data for all vegetation fires for financial years 2009/10 to 2012/13, with scores from stakeholder consultation.

Land cover class (hybrid Land Cover Map 2007/ National Forest Inventory)	Observed number of IRS points, n=964	Expected number of IRS points, based on the percentage of the study area occupied by each land cover type	Relative risk of Ignition (1 – very low; 5 – very high)	
			Empirical score	Stakeholder score
1. Broadleaved	159	139	3	2
2. Coniferous	176	165	3	3
3. Felled	6	10	2	3
4. Ground prepared for new planting	3	1	5	3
5. Mixed – predominantly Broadleaved	22	8	5	2
6. Mixed – predominantly Conifer	16	9	4	2
7. Young trees	10	5	4	4
8. Low density	0	0	1	2
9. Assumed woodland	0	0	1	2
10. Shrub land	0	1	1	4
11. Grass	102	144	2	5
12. Agricultural land	48	56	3	4
13. Other vegetation	0	0	1	5
14. Bare ground/rock	1	2	2	1
15. Urban/building	336	321	3	1
16. Quarry	1	0	5	1
17. Powerline	0	0	1	4
18. Open water	2	6	2	1
19. Forest road or track	0	0	1	2
20. Heather	12	40	2	5
21. Heather grassland	70	56	4	5

assessments, captured during two cross-sector workshops. There were 964 IRS vegetation fire points in the study area during the four financial years available to March 2013.

An IRS-based empirical method was used to calculate a relative Risk of Ignition score for each land type. The number of expected IRS vegetation fire points for a land cover class was calculated from the total number of IRS points in the study area for the four years of record, multiplied by the percentage of the study area occupied by the land cover class. For each class, scores were assigned according to the relative difference between the number of observed fires and that expected by land cover area. Scores were also compared to those derived by expert opinion drawn from the stakeholder group (see below) (Table 1).

Spatial associations were analysed between the IRS wildfire distribution and two population characteristics, population density and social deprivation, using 2011 census data (ONS, 2012). Similarly, spatial associations were analysed between IRS wildfire distribution and levels of crime.

The 'Values at Risk' module was based on energy, health, transport and the built environment as key assets identified in stakeholder workshops. We grouped these assets into three sub-modules: Human Health and Well-being, Property and Infrastructure, and Ecosystem Services. For the first sub-module, we focussed on human vulnerability to wildfire using census-based socio-economic proxies which could result in greater physical or psychological harm and higher post-fire economic impact on individuals than would be expected relative to the average population (Finlay et al., 2012). Property and Infrastructure values were organised according to the Cabinet Office (2010) framework for critical infrastructure: transport, energy, communications, emergency services, health and social services, and other property. Selected ecosystem services were used as exemplars in the third sub-module as guided by data availability. For example, areas designated for recreation were a proxy for certain cultural services in the rural-urban interface, and nature conservation areas for biodiversity.

Two cross-sector stakeholder workshops were used to elicit knowledge and aggregate judgements. Stakeholders had detailed expert knowledge of different aspects of wildfire in the study area. We used a structured

communication technique to establish consensus views amongst group members by feeding back conclusions from the first stage of consultation to a subsequent workshop two months later. A range of exercises and worksheets were used to focus discussion, force trade-offs between

competing outcomes and prompt consensus. The first workshop focused on selecting key data sets and scoring map layers such as land cover, access and local population characteristics according to their influence on Risk of Ignition. It also identified key local

assets at risk, such as health and well-being, the environment and property. The second workshop scored the relative importance of factors affecting ignition and assessed the key Values at Risk. We used sector-based follow-up meetings to evaluate the mapped outputs.

Risk of Ignition

Eighty percent of fire points concentrated in the rural-urban interface within 160m of the boundary between urban/suburban and vegetated land-uses. Fires also concentrated around access points such as paths and roads, so distance to these features and the rural-urban boundary were included as factors in WTA. There was no spatial association with population density and fire occurrence, but population density was included in the WTA model because of workshop participants' strong contention that wildfires are caused by people, so the more people in a given area, the higher the likelihood of a fire occurring. No associations were found between fire distribution and long-term unemployment or crime levels and these factors were not included.

No spatial association was found between fire distribution and 'utilities' (powerlines and railways). However, military training areas and motorways were included as Risk of Ignition factors, since military manoeuvres, maintenance operations and motor accidents had caused vegetation fires here in the past.

Participants were asked to score Risk of Ignition for each land cover class, based on the relative flammability of fuel type and relative perceived density of human use associated with it, assuming worse case conditions in the Spring. There was a clear discrepancy between participants' scores and empirical scores based on calculated difference between observed IRS fire points and expected number of fires (Table 1). Stakeholder judgement

“A key ingredient of Wildfire Threat Analysis is the incorporation of stakeholder knowledge.”

appeared to have been influenced by the absolute number of fires associated with a land cover type without allowing for relative area. Another discrepancy was possible errors in the land cover identified due to imperfect spatial accuracy of IRS recording. After due consideration in the stakeholder groups, stakeholder scores were chosen for the final Risk of Ignition model.

At the second workshop participants worked to provide an overall analytical hierarchy-based weighting (Saaty, 1987) of the chosen Risk of Ignition factors. Each map

component then underwent further GIS and statistical processing. Four versions of the Risk of Ignition map were produced to reflect varying opinions on scores and weights. Figure 1 shows the version which received most support in sector-based follow-up meetings.

Values at Risk

Human health and well-being. At the stakeholder workshops, participants were asked to score specific components that expressed degree of vulnerability (age, health, income, evacuation issues and vulnerable dwellings) on a five-point scale, and use pair-wise comparisons to elicit a more nuanced verdict. They were initially hesitant to effectively prioritise one group's well-being over another's. Health eventually emerged as the most important factor and income as the least.

Property and infrastructure.

Participants were invited to award scores within the Cabinet Office (2010) framework for critical infrastructure on a five-point scale, and encouraged to suggest and score any other assets.

Ecosystem services. Ecosystem services derived from the first workshop were divided into 'cultural' ecosystem services and 'supporting' ecosystem services. Participants were invited to adjust the scores within these groups and to list other sources of information and assign scores to them.

Finally, the three Values at Risk sub-modules were weighted according to workshop discussions that established a clear priority of human health and well-being over property and infrastructure, with ecosystem services considered of least importance. Figure 2 shows the final, agreed, version of the Values at Risk map for the area, as confirmed in the sector-based meetings.

Discussion and Conclusions

Our study has shown that GIS-based approaches such as WTA can be used to evaluate the threat of wildfire in a UK context, but need to be adapted to allow

Figure 1. Final, agreed, Risk of Ignition module map. Circular points are vegetation fires reported in the Fire Services' Incident Recording System for four financial years, 2009/10 - 2012/13. Location A marks high priority area of forest for wildfire management, located adjacent to rural-urban interface areas of high Risk of Ignition and Values at Risk.

for data availability, scale differences and limited knowledge on values at risk, especially ecosystem services. In the UK most fires at the rural-urban interface are small due to rapid suppression and small plot size. Risk of Ignition is therefore important, especially when nearly all wildfires are anthropogenic in origin.

The Swinley study was a first approach at quantifying Values at Risk, but many ecosystem services were not included as methodologies for monetising them have yet to be established. This contributed to the inability to prioritise Values at Risk, mainly because of wildfire managers' limited experience with, and access to, economic information. The lack of reliable and consistent procedures for valuing many services provided by the forestry sector is likely to hold back uptake of WTA or other wildfire risk assessment systems in the UK. In contrast, others argue that deliberative processes like WTA are a better approach to environmental decision-making than economists' valuations (Holland, 1997; Spash, 2008). Deliberative judgement may therefore be the practical limit of assessment for Values at Risk.

Despite the mix of sectors, there was a large measure of agreement over decisions made, especially in ranking people and property over ecosystem services. However, land managers were quite willing to accept empirical analysis based on IRS fire occurrence, whereas firefighters understood deficiencies in the IRS datasets.

Evaluation of wildfire threat is sensitive to local context, and the extent of the study area. Lack of association between fire occurrence and population characteristics in our study area contrasts with evidence on the location of arson in South Wales (Jollands et al., 2011), where the 20% most economically-deprived areas were nine times more likely to experience wildfires than the 20% least deprived. Crime and unemployment levels in our study area were generally low, and the distances

between contrasting areas too small to produce sufficient variety in spatial distribution. They may be more evident with a larger and more varied study area.

Our study revealed a conflict between expert judgement and empirical models based on IRS data, creating a dilemma over which to use. At the local scale, stakeholders appreciate the risk of wildfire at particular locations based on knowledge and experience. However, the shortcomings of IRS for spatial analysis at a local scale include: the limited length of record; whether ignition point, centre of

Figure 2. Final, agreed, Values at Risk module map. Contains Ordnance Survey data © Crown copyright and database right 2013. Location A marks high priority area of forest for wildfire management, located adjacent to rural-urban interface areas of high Values at Risk.

burned area, call-out or rendezvous point are recorded; omission of fires not reported to Fire Services; and estimated accuracy of damage area. Lack of close agreement between the two data sources suggests that local IRS-based models could not be justifiably used elsewhere as they are unlikely to be broadly consistent with the views of stakeholders. IRS-based empirical models would be more suited at the national scale, especially compared to the challenge of the incorporating the diversity of stakeholder interests.

The utility of WTA is its apparent simplicity. Combining Risk of Ignition, (ideally) Hazard and Values at Risk modules to generate a single threat value for each location is an exercise in data aggregation, reduction and synthesis. More importantly, it is the result of negotiation and trade-offs by appropriate professionals. Outputs could be further simplified into

“Wildfire Threat Analysis appears a valuable tool for the forestry sector.”

‘traffic-light’ zones of low, medium and high threat from which foresters could prioritise zones for wildfire management (Forestry Commission, 2014). Forestry stakeholders suggested that component maps could be used for forest planning, vegetation management and emergency planning. ‘What-if’ scenarios can be explored; for example, at location A (Figure 1), how planting deciduous trees on forest perimeters as fire breaks would change risk of ignition. Other examples include optimising the position of fire watches, suppression resources, emergency access routes, assembly points and water supplies for firefighting, and assisting swift

action in the event of a fire. Expanding suburban development is also likely to increase the need for such a discussion support tool. Forest management organisations in the UK already work with GIS systems so it would be possible to extend this to include wildfire-relevant information. Furthermore, many layers can be re-used to assess other hazards.

WTA appears a valuable tool for the forestry sector to capture and exchange a wide range of knowledge on local wildfire threat at the rural-urban interface. An extensive range of relevant stakeholders need to be involved to identify and evaluate local data and generate the map layers. Stakeholder views and empirically-based evidence sometimes diverge. Insights are highly localised and drawing conclusions is resource-intensive. At this stage and scale, WTA is not so much a decision support system for the UK as a ‘discussion support’ tool to reconcile the needs of different stakeholders and develop landscape solutions that reduce wildfire threat. Such a process is also likely to encourage buy-in to the resulting risk assessment, and we recommend it as a discussion platform to bring together all the agencies involved in assessing wildfire risk in the rural-urban interface.

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